

COMPREHENSIVE SOIL ANALYSIS USING LIBS AND VIS-NIRS

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Rapid and reliable soil assessment plays an important role in advancing sustainable land use and precision farming practices. This work focuses on the combined use of laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) and visible near-infrared spectroscopy (Vis-NIRS) as synergistic, non-destructive tools for detailed soil characterization. LIBS offers elemental analysis through plasma emission spectra on the soil surface, whereas NIRS provides insight into organic and mineralogical components based on molecular vibrations. By combining these two spectroscopic methods, the study aims to improve the accuracy of predictions for critical soil attributes such as nutrient levels, texture, and organic matter content. A set of agricultural soil samples from Denmark, including both topsoil and subsoil, was used in this study. The data obtained from LIBS and NIRS, both individually and in fusion, have been explored with the support of multivariate statistical models. Their respective and combined analytical capabilities have been studied. This approach highlights the potential for developing rapid, in-field soil assessment tools to support informed agricultural and environmental decision-making [1].

Figure 1: Soil characterization using LIBS and Vis-NIRS

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References

[1] S. Sanchez et al., Combining Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) and Visible Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (Vis-NIRS) for Soil Phosphorus Determination, *Sensors* 20(18), (2020) 5419.